

Cation Complexation and Conformational Changes of Crown Ether Complexes of Bovine Serum Albumin†

D. DASGUPTA, V. THANABAL and V. KRISHNAN*

Department of Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore-560 012

Macrocyclic polyethers, benzo-15-crown-5 and dibenzo-18-crown-6 have been coupled to bovine serum albumin (bsa) via diazotlinkage in order to elucidate the changes in conformation of the protein upon (i) conjugate formation and (ii) addition of Na⁺, K⁺ and Ca²⁺ to the crown ether moieties of the conjugate. Gel filtration studies of the coupled complex reveal the homogeneity and the presence of cross linkage in the conjugate of *cis* and *trans* dibenzo-18-crown-6. Optical absorbance, fluorescence and pmr spectroscopic studies indicate that the tyrosine moieties of the protein to be the sites of appendage of the crown ethers. Circular dichroic (CD) spectra of the bsa conjugates have shown a decrease in the ordered conformation of the protein upon conjugation and the loss in conformation follows the order, *trans*-conjugate > *cis*-conjugate > benzo-15-crown-5 conjugate. It is further pointed out that the addition of K⁺ and Ca²⁺ leads to a decrease in α -helical content of *cis*-conjugate, while Na⁺ has no perceptible effect, as observed on the addition of Na⁺ ions. The significance of these results *vis-a-vis* the role of proteins in the ion transport in presence of an ionophore is discussed.

THE crown ethers, first reported by Pederson¹, are known to selectively sequester alkali and alkaline earth cations from aqueous environments and solubilise the complexes formed in the lipid fraction of the cell membrane^{2,3}. This knowledge has triggered considerable research interest for using them as membrane-active complexones. The effect of these ionophores on the ion-transport in the respiring rat liver mitochondria has shown that the uptake of crown ether by mitochondria is related to the cation complexing ability of the ionophore^{4,5}. Despite this, information regarding the behaviour of crown ether in membrane which is a two dimensional solution of globular integral proteins dispersed in a fluid lipid matrix, are wanting⁶. The crown ether in such matrix can also interact with proteins. The importance of proteins is clearly brought about in a demonstration of the change in conformational feature of a protein during ion-transport process. Our interest has been in the development of macrocyclic entities in general, and crown ethers in particular, as ionophores to understand the mode of uptake and delivery of cations across a membrane. Earlier we investigated the ionophoric behaviour of several metallo crown porphyrins and demonstrated metal dependent uncoupling of mitochondrial energy potential⁷. Here, we examine the cation complexation properties and accompanying conformational changes of crown ether conjugates of a protein.

This report deals with the coupling reaction of two crown ethers, benzo-15-crown-5 (1) and dibenzo-18-crown-6 (2) with a representative protein, bovine serum albumin (bsa) and a study of the changes in conformation of the protein resulting

from (i) the appendage of the crown ether followed by (ii) the encapsulation of the metal ion by the crown ether moiety. The choice of bsa as the protein, in spite of it being a serum protein, is that it has been characterised well and its properties well documented. Apart from this, these conjugates afford a bsa-hapten conjugate to raise antibody of crown ethers in order to study its immunological properties⁸. Such possibilities are even more important in view of the limited pharmacological study of these crown ethers⁹.

Experimental

bsa and tris-HCl buffer were obtained from Sigma Chemicals, USA. The column materials, Sephadex G-200 and Sepharose 4B used for gel chromatography were from Pharmacia Fine Chemicals, Sweden. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. Water used in the preparation of buffers was double-distilled and deionised by passing through Chelex-100 resin.

The 4'-aminobenzo-15-crown-5, *cis*- and *trans*-diaminodibenzo-18-crown-6 were synthesised and diazotised using the procedure described earlier¹⁰. The coupling of the arenediazonium ethers to bsa was accomplished by adopting a procedure similar to the one employed for *p*-aminobenzoic acid to bsa⁸. A pH of 9-9.5 was maintained during the coupling reaction at 0-5°. The reaction mixture was dialysed extensively at 0° until the dialysate was free from any unreacted diazonium salts as apparent from the absence of any absorbance at 400 nm. It was then lyophilised and stored below

† Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

0° for subsequent use. The spectrometers employed were Beckman 26 (for absorption), Perkin-Elmer fluorescence spectrometer and Bruker FT. 270 MHz nmr spectrometer. The CD spectra were recorded on a Jasco 10 spectropolarimeter calibrated with camphor-d-10-sulphonic acid¹⁰. Cells of the path lengths of 1 mm and 0.5 mm were employed for recording the spectra in the far-uv region, 210-250 nm.

Results and Discussion

The facile completion of the diazo coupling reaction is evidenced from the color of lyophilised product. The structural integrity of the products was established using gel filtration, optical absorption, fluorescence, and ¹H nmr spectral methods.

A comparison of the elution profile of bsa and 1-conjugate of bsa employing Sephadex G-200 (Fig. 1a) shows the homogeneity of the protein as indicated by the appearance of single peak. The elution profile for the 1-conjugate suggests a marginal net increase in the molecular weight which results from the appendage of the crown ether to the protein. The intactness of the 17-disulphide bridges of the protein in the conjugate is apparent from the elution profile of the conjugate which is eluted in a single peak and has no other peak to the right of that single peak. Similar experiments for *cis*-2 and *trans*-2 appended bsa revealed that the eluate comes within the void volume of Sephadex G-200 indicating a molecular weight of 20 k daltons (Fig. 1b) for these conjugates. This could arise because of the extensive cross linking in the protein due to the presence two diazo groups in the crown ethers. However, the homogeneity of these products are seen from the single elution peak when Sepharose 4B is employed.

Apart from the elution profile of the conjugates as mentioned above, the absorption spectra in both uv and visible regions also indicate the presence of the covalently coupled crown ether in the protein. Fig. 2a shows the uv spectra of the bsa and the coupled crown ether conjugates. The relative enhancement in the 280 nm band as observed for

Fig 1. (a) The elution profile of (■) bsa and (Δ) benzo-15-crown-5-conjugate through a Sephadex G-200 column (34 cm × 1 cm) at a flow rate of 3 ml h⁻¹. The eluent was double-distilled deionised water at pH 7.0. The optical density of the fractions had been measured at 280 nm. (b) The elution profile of (●) *cis*- and (□) *trans*-dibenzo 18-crown-6 through the same column as mentioned above under the identical conditions. The optical density of the fractions had been measured at 370 nm. The arrows indicate the void volume as measured by means of blue dextran.

Fig 2. (a) UV spectra of (—) bovine serum albumin, (---) benzo-15-crown-5-conjugate, (- - -) *cis*-dibenzo-18-crown-6-conjugate and (— · —) *trans*-dibenzo-18-crown-6-conjugate at pH 7.0 and 20°. The concentrations of all are 1 mg ml⁻¹ (b) The visible spectra of (—) *cis*-dibenzo-18-crown-6-conjugate and (---) *trans*-dibenzo-18-crown-6 at pH 7.0 and 20°. The concentration of both are 0.5 mg ml⁻¹

the conjugates, is traced to the presence of additional aromatic groups from the appended crown ether part. In addition, the broad band in the visible spectra of the complex conjugates (Fig. 2b) provides sufficient proof for the presence of diazo chromophore. The interesting question as to which of the possible amino acid residues in bsa, the crown ethers are attached is worthy of consideration. Among the number of amino acid (aa) residues in bsa, tyr, his, trp, lys and arg are the possible sites that can be covalently linked to diazo groups. Of these tyrosine has the highest affinity for such diazo coupling reaction⁹. The site of coupling can be judged from the ratio of the number of moles of arenediazonium salt and bsa (in terms of amino acid residues) employed for the coupling reaction. It is worthy to mention at this point that there are 19 tyrosine residues in bsa and an employ of 20 moles of arenediazonium salt as used in the present study would essentially couple all the tyrosine residues.

The site of binding of crown moiety to bsa is sought from fluorescence studies. It is observed that there is a marked decrease in the fluorescence intensity of the crown ether conjugates when excited at 278 nm corresponding to tyrosine absorption as compared to the bsa alone (Fig. 3). The quenching can be ascribed to the energy transfer between tyr and the coupled crown ethers containing the aryl rings. The examples of such energy transfer leading to fluorescence quenching of the proteins (enzyme, like carboxypeptidase) in presence of bound dansyl group as observed in enzyme(carboxypeptidase)-substrate complex have been reported

Fig 3 Fluorescence emission spectrum of (a) bsa (0.2 mg ml⁻¹) and (b) benzo-15-crown-5-conjugate (0.2 mg ml⁻¹) excited at 278 nm at pH 7.0 and 25°.

earlier¹¹. That the coupling has taken place predominantly to the tyr residues of the bsa is further shown from the ¹H nmr spectrum of 1-conjugate of the protein. The observed line broadening of the aryl protein signals (at δ 7-8) of the conjugates supports the presence of the coupled tyr residues.

The above spectroscopic studies apart from showing the homogeneous nature of the conjugates, also reveal the tyrosine residues as the sites of

Fig. 4. (a) Far-uv OD spectra of (—) bsa, (---) benzo-15-crown-5-conjugate, (- - -) *cis*-dibenzo-18-crown-6-conjugate, and (-.-) *trans*-dibenzo-18-crown-6-conjugate at pH 7.0 and 20°. The ordinate represents the observed dichrograph record unconverted into the molar ellipticity scale since the concentrations of all the solutions were maintained at 5 mg ml⁻¹ and the path length of the cell was kept fixed. (b) The CD spectra of *cis*-dibenzo-18-crown-6 conjugate (5 mg ml⁻¹) in presence of (---) NaCl (100 M), (—) KCl (100 mM) and (-.-) CaCl₂ (100 mM) at pH 7.0 and 20°.

attachments for the crown ethers. However, the possibility of binding to other amino acids which appears very remote from stoichiometric considerations can not be totally eliminated from these studies. It is of interest to study by means of CD spectroscopy the cation complexation properties of the appended crown ethers and investigate the conformational features arising from the backbone structure of the protein.

The far-uv CD spectra of the bsa along with those of the crown ether conjugates in the region 210-250 nm (Fig. 4a) reveal a change in the conformation of bsa. The spectra as depicted are not converted into molar ellipticity scale since the concentrations of all the solutions are maintained at 5 mg ml⁻¹ and the path length of the cell has been kept fixed at 0.5 mm. The lower dichroic values (θ_{222}) in the conjugates represent less α -helical content in the bsa¹². Thus, the α -helicity of the protein, bsa, decreases with the nature of the appended ether and follows the order *trans*-2 > *cis*-2 > 1. Along with the above observed changes in the dichroic absorption in the far-uv region, there is a feeble dichroic band observed around the 350-450 nm region corresponding to the diazo chromophore. Since this band is very small in magnitude, it was not studied in detail. However, the presence of such a band lends further support to the coupling of crown ether to the protein.

With the two-fold objectives of studying the capacity of appended crown ethers to encapsulate the cations and the changes in conformation of the protein that ensues the ion encapsulation, we examined the CD spectra of crown ether conjugate proteins in presence of varying amounts of different

cations K⁺, Na⁺ and Ca²⁺. The effects that may arise from any non-specific absorption of cations by bsa alone is discounted by running the spectrum of bsa under similar conditions. Addition of cations, Na⁺, K⁺ and Ca²⁺ to 1-, and *trans*-2-conjugates does not produce any appreciable changes in the ellipticity (θ_{222}) values (Fig. 5). Interestingly, considerable decrease in the dichroic value was observed for the *cis*-2-complex (Fig. 4b). The decrease in α -helical content of *cis*-2-conjugate on addition of K⁺ is more pronounced than that of Na⁺, paralleling increased stability of K⁺-2 complex compared to that of Na⁺-2 complex. Similar trend is also observed for the *trans*-2-conjugate though the change in the magnitude of (θ_{222}) value is small. It is worthwhile to note that with the addition of K⁺ and Ca²⁺, there was approximately 50% decrease in the value of ellipticity (θ_{222}), indicating a dramatic loss in α -helicity on cation complexation (Figs. 4b and 5).

An explanation as to the further loss in α -helical content of the conjugate protein on cation complexation can be viewed from the repulsions set up by the cations encapsulated in the appended crown ethers. This becomes more obvious due to clustering of tyr residues in domains I and II (Fig. 6). The cross linking that occurs in *cis*- and *trans*-2-conjugates, in fact, should promote random orientation of the ether moieties and hence, disordered cation occupation. We expect the decrease in α -helical content to be the same in both the conjugates. However, the reason for the different behaviour remains uncertain.

The aforementioned result point out that (i) there is a net change in the conformation of bovine

Fig. 5.—Percentage decrease in the mean residual molar ellipticity value (at 221 nm) of benzo-15-crown-5-conjugate, cis- and trans-dibenzo-18-crown-conjugates as a function of the changes in the concentrations of metal ions. The mean residual molar ellipticity has been calculated from the relation: $\theta_{221} = D_{1cm} \times M / 10 \times 3300$ ($K \text{ cm}^2 \text{ dmol}^{-1}$), where D and M denotes the observed dichrograph record and the mean residue weight of the amino acids in the protein, respectively.

serum albumin due to coupling with the crown ethers; the extent of change depends upon the nature of crown ethers and (ii) the encapsulation of cations by certain crown ethers changes the protein conformation, the extent of change that results, depends also upon the nature of cation.

The ionophoric activity of these crown ethers have so far been understood only in terms of the solubility of their cation complexes in the lipid bilayer leading to the eventual transport of the cations across the membrane. Notwithstanding the limitation that bsa is a serum protein, the present observations are significant from the point of view underlying the possible role of proteins during the ion transport even in presence of the ionophore, crown ether.

Fig. 6. The relative positions of the tyrosine residues in the primary sequence of bsa (primary sequence of bsa taken from J. R. Brown, F.E.B.S., 11th Meeting, Copenhagen, 1977, 50).

Acknowledgement

The work is supported by Department of Science and Technology, Government of India. One of the authors (V.T.) is thankful to Department of Atomic Energy, Government of India, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

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